

SUPPLEMENT F: PREDICTION CERTAINTIES FROM FIGURE 5 FOR PHARMGKB AND DRUGBANK

We include two files with EBC's scores for the PGx and drug-target prediction tasks on the dense matrix. These are the raw scores used in the generation of the dendrogram in Figure 5. The names of the files are:

pgx-predictions.tsv
(PGx prediction scores)

drugtarget-predictions.tsv
(drug-target prediction scores)

The columns within these files are:

drug-gene-pair score indicator-if-known

The last column, obviously, is meaningless, since none of the pairs in these files are known PGx or drug-target relationships.